

Factors Affecting the Decision to Play Online Game via Mobile Phone

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Abstract:- The objectives of this research: 1) to explore the personal factors of those who play online games via mobile phones; 2) to study the psychological factors that affect the decision to play online games via mobile phones; 3) to study the decision to play online games via mobile phones. This research is quantitative research. The population was who use online game services via mobile phones in Thailand which the exact number is unknown. A sample of 400 people was used by specific random sampling. By using questionnaires as a tool to collect data statistics used in the analysis These are frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. and the statistics used in the test multiple Linear regression analysis.

The research finding were found that: 1) personal factors, including gender, age, status, education level, occupation, and different monthly incomes, affected the decision to play online games via mobile phones.; 2) who used online game services via mobile phones gave the most importance to the lifestyle factor, followed by the attitude factor and the acceptance of technology factor and 3) the personal factors and psychological factors were related to the decision to play online game via mobile phone.

Keywords:- Motivation, Online Game, Via Mobile Phone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile games are one of the applications that we can easily download, whether it is Android or IOS. If we are interested in any game, we can search for reviews on the internet. Each game has a different way of playing. It is interesting and attracts us to sit and play all day and night. If we are mature enough, we can distinguish when to play games or work. However, if we are still children, it may cause us to become addicted to our mobile phones. Although mobile games may cause harm if we play too much or do not know the time, they are quite useful. The obvious benefit of mobile games is that they make us relax because the game makes us feel fun and happy playing our favorite games. They must be easy to play, do not have to think too much, and have beautiful graphics. This will help us relax more. The next benefit is that it will help us plan and solve immediate problems, such as war games, treasure hunt games, which require planning so that we can achieve our goals or win the game. However, if our plan does not work, we have to think of a solution right then and there because if we do not think of a solution, we may lose the game.

Therefore, mobile games are also useful. In addition, some mobile games can also help develop our skills, such as spot the difference games, fill in the puzzles, and quiz games because they will help don't want their children to play useless games, just download the game for them. So they can choose for themselves. But if they are teenagers, they have to warn them a bit so that they don't ruin their studies. As for working age, they can probably differentiate. There's nothing to worry about. Therefore, mobile games are more useful than we think.

There are many types of mobile games. First, we have to choose according to our preferences. But if the game uses a lot of memory but our mobile phone may not support it well enough, it will cause the game to lag or be slow. Therefore, we have to consider the memory in our mobile phone. But for children, parents should control it a bit because there are many types of mobile games. Some are not suitable for children, such as games with fighting, which are usually marked with a number that indicates how old the child is. Or parents must also consider the appropriateness, but no matter what age you are, mobile games are considered something that can help you relieve stress and be happier, but you must play in moderation because if you are too addicted, it may affect your studies, work, and health because you have to use your eyes and fingers to play, which may cause eye pain or shoulder or neck pain. But believe me, if you play mindfully, mobile games will be more beneficial than you think (Mobile Games and Benefits, 2017).

➤ Research Objective

The Researcher is Interested in Studying;

- To explore the personal factors of those who play online games via mobile phones
- To study the psychological factors that affect the decision to play online games via mobile phones
- To study the decision to play online games via mobile phones

➤ Research Hypothesis

The Assumptions Provided in this Article are as Follows:

- H1: Personal factor that affect work efficiency of the workers in Chengdu
- H2: Motivation factors affecting the effectiveness of the workers in Chengdu

➤ *Research Framework*

Fig.1 Research Framework

➤ *Definitions of Specific Terms*

- Attitude refers to a person's readiness to show behavior in support or opposition to a person, institution, situation or idea (Howard H. Kendler, 1963).
- Acceptance of technology refers to an important factor in using and living with technology. The use of technology creates experiences, knowledge, skills and the need to use technology.
- Lifestyle refers to the overall structure of life, time use and spending of individuals. Lifestyle reflects the activities, interests and opinions of individuals very well. It can also reflect the values of individuals through activities or situations that occur around individuals. In addition, lifestyles are something that can change rapidly according to the changing environment and society. Therefore, those who want to study lifestyles should always follow the current movements and situations in order to be able to understand and be aware of the changing lifestyles.
- Decision-making refers to the process of choosing to act. One of the choices that consumers always have to make decisions about the choices of products and services. They will choose products or services based on information and limitations of the situation. Therefore, decision-making is an important process that is in the minds of consumers (Chatyaporn Samojai, 2007).
- Games refer to activities that are done for entertainment, for learning, for education, to practice thinking skills and abilities. In the past, games were physical activities, but at present, they have been created in the form of software programs through various devices such as computers or mobile phones.
- Online games refer to games that have multiple players in each game, via the Internet, where characters play as our representatives and talk to people in the game. They can also create a society to help each other fight and collect experience points.

- Mobile phones refer to electronic devices used for two-way communication via mobile phones, using radio waves to contact mobile phone networks through base stations. Each mobile phone network is connected to the landline network and the mobile phone networks of other service providers. Mobile phones with increased capabilities in the form of portable computers are referred to as mobile phones.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The research results useful and achieving the established literature review is divided into 3 parts:

- A. *Theory of Personal Factors*
- B. *Theory of Psychological*
- C. *Theory of Decision Making*
- D. *Related Research*

A. *Theory of Personal Factors*

Kotler et al., (2018) defined demographic characteristics. (Demographic) divided into 5 questions to be solved

- Gender is a specific characteristic that is inherent to each person since birth. They are divided into females and males, which have differences in physical characteristics, thoughts, attitudes, behaviors, perceptions, values, and communication.
- Age (Age) is an indicator of the identity of each person, indicating maturity. And the ability to recognize and understand different experiences is influenced by past perceptions that are more or less different. People with different backgrounds affect emotions, understanding, perception, thought processes. and different decisions
- Education level has an effect on a person's attitude, thoughts, and beliefs. Values, ideology, choosing to receive information, understanding in detail and clearly will have different behavior. People who have received a higher education will have more skills in perception and Thinking results in a good

understanding of things and believing in things that are reasonable.

- Occupation (Occupation) is an indicator of the characteristics and abilities of each person, including the period of exposure to news. You can learn more than your own occupation, such as gathering with people who work in other occupations. It will make you have knowledge and interest. More broadly, different careers result in different values and perceptions.
- Income (Income) is an indicator of the spending potential of each person. People with low economic and social status, low income will have the potential to spend goods or various services, as well as being able to receive information well and will seek benefits to make themselves earn more income. Restrictions on learning and experience affect those who have education. Oh, because I have a low economic status.

As people age, their life cycle varies, and consumer behavior also changes accordingly. Single young people are more likely to spend money on education, leisure and entertainment, and purchasing high-end consumer goods. For example, the emergence of the "new poor" in modern cities. They are representatives of young people who are single, high paying, high spending, and have no savings. They are advocates of a new life, daring to try new products, but not too concerned about prices. The elderly are the main consumer group of various health products. Middle aged people are more inclined to spend money on children. For young people who have just started a family, durable consumer goods such as houses and household appliances will account for a large proportion of expenses.

There are also gender differences in purchasing decisions. Due to the different ways of thinking among men, their logical thinking is strong, resulting in a short time to make purchase decisions. When selecting products, they are rough and quick, generally focusing on the quality and practical utility of the products, and rarely paying attention to the appearance and packaging of the products. Women have strong visual thinking abilities and profound emotional experiences. Therefore, they take a relatively long time to make purchasing decisions, carefully select products, and pay attention to the style, appearance, packaging, and other aspects of the products.

Professional needs will lead to corresponding purchasing behavior. A blue collar worker would purchase work clothes, work shoes, etc. The senior manager of the 8 company will purchase expensive suits, go to high-end clubs for consumption, and so on. A person's financial situation can greatly affect their choice of products. A person with a high income and a large amount of savings has the ability to purchase products with higher prices, and their impulse to shop will also greatly increase. On the contrary, consider cheap goods and tend to be cautious and conservative when shopping.

B. Theory of Psychological

Attitude is a very important concept in social psychology and communication and has been widely used. To define the term attitude, many scholars have defined it as follows:

Carter V. Good (1959) stated that attitude is the readiness to express in a way that supports or opposes a certain situation, person or thing. Newcomb (1854) stated that attitudes that exist in

a particular person depend on the environment and may be expressed in behaviors that are possible in two ways: a liking or liking that makes others want to be close to that thing or another characteristic expressed in the form of dissatisfaction or hatred that does not want to be close to that thing. Therefore, it can be concluded that attitude is a relationship between feelings and beliefs or perceptions of a person and a tendency to react in some way to the target of that attitude. Attitude affects the expression of behavior. It can be seen that attitudes consist of thoughts that affect emotions and feelings through behavior.

C. Theory of Decision Making

Consumer purchasing decision refers to the process in which consumers carefully evaluate the attributes of a product, brand, or service and make choices to purchase products that meet a specific need. The broad consumer purchasing decision refers to the process of analyzing, evaluating, selecting, and implementing the best purchasing plan among two or more available purchasing plans, as well as post purchase evaluation, under the control of a certain purchasing motivation, in order to meet a certain demand. It is a systematic decision-making process that includes the determination of requirements, the formation of purchasing motivation, the selection and implementation of purchasing plans, and post purchase evaluation.

Song Zhijie, Tang Xiaoli. (2016) Based on the cue theory and cognitive decision-making principle, this paper uses eye movement experiment method to explore the mechanism of two important cues in Online shopping: price and evaluation influencing consumers' purchase decisions. The research shows that consumers will use price and evaluation to evaluate products and follow the cognitive decision-making principle of Bounded rationality; But consumers pay more attention to the reference value of evaluation clues, and when the two clues have the same valence, consumers will adopt deeper cognitive processing methods.

Hu man (2008) Philip Kotler proposed a simple consumer purchasing behavior model in his book "Marketing Management (Asia)". In this model, Kotler believes that consumer behavior patterns typically consist of three parts. The first part includes internal marketing stimuli and external environmental stimuli, which work together to attract consumers' attention. The second part includes two intermediary factors: the buyer's characteristics and the buyer's decision-making process, which handle the stimuli received. The third part is the result of processing, which refers to the actual externalization of consumer purchasing behavior, including product brand selection and purchase timing.

The decision-making process section, which is the core focus of the EKB model, explains the five stages of the purchase decision-making process as follows:

➤ Problem cognition

The cognition of problems is the first stage of the decision-making process. When consumers perceive a gap between their ideal and actual state, they will generate problem cognition, which mainly comes from two aspects: first, internal motivation, such as physiological needs; The second is external stimuli, such as advertising messages, that awaken consumers' perceived needs.

➤ Information seeking

After consumers have a problem perception, they start searching for relevant information. When an individual's existing memory and signals are sufficient to solve the problem, they can proceed to the next stage of action; Otherwise, it is necessary to search the outside world. The channels for information sources have three directions: public sources, commercial sources, and personal sources.

➤ Program evaluation

After consumers understand the situation related to mobile phones, they evaluate various possible solutions, including the following four parts:

• Evaluation criteria:

The factors or standards used by consumers to evaluate products, usually represented by product attributes or specifications, and the selection of evaluation criteria is influenced by personal motivation, lifestyle, and personality.

• Belief:

Consumers evaluate each solution or brand based on various evaluation criteria.

• Attitude:

Provide consumers with a comprehensive evaluation of various solutions or brands based on various evaluation criteria, resulting in a consistent level of preference for each solution or brand.

• Willingness:

Refers to the subjective probability of consumers choosing a specific solution or brand, which is influenced by the normative influence of the reference group or family members.

➤ Purchase Selection

After the evaluation of each Program evaluation, consumers will choose a plan that best solves the original problem and take purchase action. Generally speaking, when consumers have a positive attitude towards a certain product or brand, the higher their willingness to purchase, the greater their chances of choosing the product or brand. However, consumers may also be affected by unexpected situations.

➤ 5) Purchase Results

After making a choice, consumers who are satisfied with the result will enhance their beliefs and store them in their memory, increasing the chances of future repurchase. If the result is not satisfactory, it will lead to disappointment and continue to seek information from the outside world to reduce the feeling of imbalance.

D. Related Research

Thanapat Emabut (2014) studied "Factors Influencing the Decision to Play Online Games of People in Bangkok in 2015". The results of the study found that most of the respondents were male, aged 21-25 years, single, working as company employees, had a bachelor's degree, and had an average income of 10,000-20,000 baht per month. The frequency of playing online games was 2-5 times/month. The average duration of playing online games was 1-3 hours/day. The normal time spent playing online

games was 6.00 - 12.00 (evening - night). The average cost of using online games was never topping up or paying for services. The reason for deciding to play online games was to relax and find something to do in free time.

Naronnarit Rattanapimol (2017) studied "Marketing Mix Factors Influencing the Choice to Play Games via Mobile Devices". The results of the study found that the factors influencing the choice to play games via mobile devices were factors related to the creation and presentation of physical characteristics. And the process, product factors, game popularity factors, and features that stimulate group competition. Finally, the price factor for demographic factors, it was found that different genders have different decisions to choose to play games via mobile devices. Women have a higher average decision level in choosing to play games via mobile devices than men. In addition, it was found that respondents with different incomes have different decisions to choose to play games via mobile devices. Those with an average monthly income of 30,001 - 40,000 baht have a higher average decision level in choosing to play games than those with an average monthly income of other groups.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researchers conducted the research according to the research process and quantitative research methods. This is a descriptive study by using questionnaires to collect information from population samples. The research mainly adopts the methods of literature research, interview and questionnaire.

➤ *Population and Sample*

The population studied in this study were who use online game services via mobile phones in Thailand which the exact number is unknown. The sample group in the study was 246 Sample sizes were determined from Taro Yamane's formula (1973) at 95% confidence level and tolerances of 5% sample selection were accepted 400 totals.

➤ *Research Tools*

Research object: after the questionnaire is designed, in order to ensure the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, this study first conducted a pre-test on a small part of the sample population. At the same time, we conducted in-depth interviews with 100 consumers who use online game services via mobile phones in Thailand, avoided unclear expression and ambiguous understanding in the questionnaire as far as possible, deleted the options that are not easy to understand and repeat, and formed a formal questionnaire with small samples.

- The general information of the respondents is as follows: consumers and friends who purchased smart phones sent out 400 questionnaires.
- The respondents' opinions are as follows: the first determinant of the sample populations who use online game services via mobile phones in Thailand. Compared with ordinary agricultural chemical, consumers are more willing to buy s agricultural chemical and are willing to pay high prices for them because of their powerful functions.

Secondly, from the analysis results, the second influencing factor is the brand. It can be seen that when people buy agricultural chemical, the brand has become a more important factor after the

function, especially in the consumer group. Through further analysis of the questionnaire, in the questionnaire, some subjects' reference price index is greater than or equal to 1, and some of them have the same demand for the brand as or even slightly higher than the latter, this is enough to show that consumers are very keen on brands.

By using the Likert scale, it is divided into five levels, namely 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = neutral, 2 = disagree, 1 = strongly disagree.

➤ *Data Collection Methods*

This is the data collected by the researchers:

- Basic data were collected from the questionnaire survey of the sampling group.
- Assistant Data Researchers collect data from studies of relevant documents.

➤ *The Statistics Used in Data Analysis*

Descriptive statistical analysis. Part 1 of the questionnaire uses frequency, percentage, mean and Part 2 uses the mean standard deviation to describe the general information from the sample and the analysis of opinion data, independent variables and dependent variables. The criteria for interpreting the results are as follows:

When analyzing the data, the students collected all the scores to find the mean and standard deviation of the sample based on the criteria according to which the question is a scoring scale, which is divided into 5 levels.

Score Level:

- Strongly Agree means a score of 5 points
- Agree means a score of 4 points
- Neutral means a score of 3 points
- Disagree means a score of 2 points
- Strongly Disagree means a score of 1 point

Therefore, the criteria for interpreting to classify the mean into the following ranges:

- Average score between 4.20–5.00 means Strongly Agree
- Average score between 3.40 – 4.19 means Agree
- Average score between 2.60 – 3.39 means Neutral
- Average score between 1.80 – 2.59 means Disagree
- Average score between 1.00 – 1.79 means Strongly Disagree

IV. RESULTS

The researcher has summarized the results of the research as follows:

A. Demographic Factors Affecting the Decision to Play Online Games via Mobile Phones

The research results found that most of the users of online games via mobile phones were male, 232 people, or 58 percent, aged 21-30 years, 343 people, or 85.80 percent, and 378 people, or 94.50 percent, were single. 261 people, or 65.30 percent, held a bachelor's degree, and 135 people, or 33.80 percent, were students. 201 people, or 50.30 percent, had an income of 10,000-20,000 baht. The research results found that personal factors, including gender, age, status, education level, occupation, and different monthly incomes, affected the decision to play online games via mobile phones. 2. Psychological factors are related to the decision to play online games via mobile phones. The research results found that users of online games via mobile phones gave the most importance to psychological factors in their decision to play online games via mobile phones overall. The mean score was 4.46. When considering the details in each aspect, it was found that those who used online game services via mobile phones gave the most importance to the lifestyle factor with the mean score of 4.66, followed by the attitude factor with the mean score of 4.50, and the acceptance of technology factor was given the last importance with the mean score of 4.22, respectively.

➤ *Information on factors affecting the decision to play online games via mobile phones*

Table 1 Psychological Factors are Related to the Decision to Play Online Games via Mobile Phones Attitude

Attitude	\bar{x}	S.D.	viewpoint
You think that playing online games is a useful way to spend free time.	3.75	0.829	Agree
You understand that playing online games is just one activity.	3.21	0.886	Neutral
You think that playing online games is Relaxing	3.21	0.864	Neutral
You think that playing online games can build relationships with other people.	3.19	0.759	Neutral
You think that the advantage of online games is that they are available 24 hours a day.	2.82	0.831	Neutral
You think that playing online games can generate income for yourself.	4.01	1.112	Agree
You think that the staff are enthusiastic in giving advice.	3.94	0.883	Agree
You think that you can contact the Call Center immediately when you have a problem using the service.	3.18	0.989	Neutral
You think that playing online games helps you develop various skills.	3.48	0.749	Agree
total	3.42	0.878	Agree

Table 2 Psychological Factors are Related. The Decision to Play Online Games via Mobile Phones in Terms of Technology Acceptance

Technology acceptance	\bar{x}	S.D.	viewpoint
The online game system is easy to use.	3.24	0.779	Neutral
Mobile phone system to support the game	3.07	0.804	Neutral
The online game system is not complicated.	3.39	0.803	Neutral
The steps to use the online game service are easy and not complicated.	3.3	0.676	Neutral
The game operating system helps to process conveniently and quickly.	3.28	0.669	Neutral
Quality of the phone used to play the game	3.06	0.845	Neutral
The online game operating system affects the decision to use it.	3.28	0.784	Neutral
The operating system of the phone used to play the game	3.19	0.793	Neutral
The online game operating system helps to coordinate between different parties, such as chatting, using various commands without any problems.	3.32	0.834	Neutral
total	3.24	0.776	Neutral

Table 3 Psychological Factors are Related to the Decision to Play Online Games via Mobile Phones in Terms of Lifestyle.

Terms of lifestyle	\bar{x}	S.D.	viewpoint
Society influences the decision to play online games via mobile phones	3.45	0.842	Agree
Culture influences the choice to play online games via mobile phones	3.66	0.931	Agree
Game values influence the decision to play games via your mobile phones	3.33	0.851	Neutral
You decide to play online games via mobile phones because of your friends or acquaintances	3.56	0.982	Agree
You decide to buy a mobile phone to play games first	3.93	1.141	Agree
You choose to play online games by considering the quality of the game first	3.3	0.837	Neutral
You choose to play online games by thinking of the company that provides online games first	3.98	1.056	Agree
You are interested in following the news of new online games	4.03	0.856	Agree
When there is a new online game, you are interested in trying it out	3.85	0.928	Agree
total	3.67	0.936	Agree

Table 4 Decision Making to Play Online Games via Mobile Phones. Decision Making to Play Online Games via Mobile Phones.

Decision	\bar{x}	S.D.	viewpoint
Quality of online games	3.46	0.846	Agree
Variety of online games	3.47	0.864	Agree
Channels for downloading online games	3.4	1.115	Neutral
Price of online games sold	4	1.001	Agree
Promotional activities, discounts, exchanges, freebies, and giveaways of online games	3.5	0.923	Agree
total	3.56	0.950	Agree

V. DISCUSSION

➤ Personal factors, including gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation and monthly income level, are related to the decision to play online games via mobile phones. This is because the decision to play online games is different according to personal factors. People with different genders have different decisions to play online games. People with different ages have different decisions to play online games based on their experiences and attitudes. People with different marital status have different decisions to play online games based on their marital status. People with different education

levels have different decisions to play online games based on the quality of the game. People with different occupations have different ideas about deciding to play online games based on their occupations. People who play online games with high incomes have different decisions to play online games than people with low incomes who have to consider their decisions, which is consistent with the concept of Belch (2005) who mentioned personal factors, including gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation and monthly income level, which are linked to consumer demand, decision-making behavior and product usage rate, which can be accessed and effective in determining the target market, affecting

- purchasing decision-making behavior, which tends to be closely related in a cause-and-effect relationship.
- People who play online games via mobile phones give the most importance to psychological factors that affect the decision to play online games via mobile phones. This is because before gamers decide to play online games via mobile phones, they must study and search for information to evaluate alternatives in order to decide to play online games via mobile phones. In evaluating alternatives, online gamers will consider or give importance to the quality of online games, the variety of online games, easy and convenient channels to download online games, appropriate pricing of online games, and promotional activities to reduce, exchange, and give away freebies of online games, which is consistent with the concept of Ratcha Siritwat (2017) who mentioned psychological factors or internal factors that consumers' purchase of products or services is influenced by psychological factors, which are considered internal factors of consumers that influence purchasing behavior and product usage. Internal factors
 - From the analysis results, it was found that the decision to play online games via mobile phones, including the quality of online games and the variety of online games, is related to the decision to play online games via mobile phones. This may be due to psychological factors, which are considered factors that help stimulate users to want to play games. Barnard (1938) defined decision-making as a technique to consider various alternatives until there is only one option left.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

From the research results on factors affecting the decision to play online games via mobile phones, the results can be summarized as follows: Recommendations for this research from the results of this research, it was found that those who play online games via mobile phones have the highest decision to play based on the quality of the online game. Business owners who provide online games via mobile phones should focus on producing quality games because the main factor in attracting players is the fun of playing. These elements include details of images, sounds, and modern game systems that can create challenges for players, thus increasing the fun.

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